

Graduate's Employment Status: A Tracer Study for the Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management of the University of Cebu Main-Campus, Academic Year 2020-2023

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Mario Ramil R. Pepito, PhD.

Dean, College of Hotel and Restaurant Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus
ORCID:0000-0001-7716-5776| pepitomarioramil68@gmail.com

Victoria S. Amadora, PhD.

Professor, College of Hotel and Restaurant Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus
ORCID: 0009-0005-1576-6599 | victoria_amadora@hotmail.com

Earl Dave V. Rocha, PhD.

Professor, College of Hotel and Restaurant Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus
ORCID: 0000-0002-7286-1673 | earluc@gmail.com

Roselio Talamo

Faculty Member, College of Hotel and Restaurant Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus

Rona Marie Reblora

Faculty Member, College of Hotel and Restaurant Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus

Abstract

The primary aim of this study is to assess the employability and status of graduates from the College of Hospitality Management after they have completed all academic requirements at the University of Cebu during the school years 2020 to 2023. Specifically, the study investigates job-related information for graduates, aiming to assist them in navigating the rapidly changing and competitive world of tourism and hospitality. Additionally, the research examines the relevance of the current program curriculum in relation to industry needs, with the goal of making recommendations for revisions that will enhance graduate employability. This tracer study employs a descriptive research design, with 81 Hospitality Management Graduates from the specified period as respondents. The primary research instrument is a survey questionnaire, adapted from the university's research office and modified for this study. The graduates also highlight the relevance of their current curriculum to industry demands and identify specific skills acquired during their education, such as food and beverage management, bar tending, and housekeeping services. The majority of our graduates are actively employed in the field of hospitality management, particularly within the Food and Beverage departments of hotels and resorts. They express satisfaction with their salaries and wages, as well as an awareness of the career challenges inherent in the industry. Notably, most graduates secure employment within one year after graduation, thanks to the strong linkages between the school and industry properties. In terms of soft skills, communication skills rank as the most important, followed closely by human relations skills—both of which are crucial in the service-oriented tourism and hospitality industry. The college should also strengthen coordination with hotel partners to stay informed about the latest updates and employment opportunities. Simultaneously, the university must intensify efforts to support graduates in their transition to the workforce.

Keywords: UC-Main Hospitality, Hospitality Tracer, UC-Main Tracer Study ,Hospitality Management Employability Tracer

Introduction

The primary aimed of this study to identify the status of graduates and employ-ability in the college of hospitality management after they completed all academic requirements of the university for the school year 2020 to 2022 .Specifically ,the study sought the graduate job related information as to help them with their future employment to the fast changing and competitive world tourism and hospitality industry. The study also identifies factors like job placement, reasons for employment, salaries and wages, new hotel and restaurant human resources needed, skills ,knowledge and values that contributes to the graduates employ-ability. Furthermore the study sought the relevance of the present program curriculum versus the needs of the industry as to make recommendations revisions to increase the graduate employ-ability rate. A tracer study or graduate survey is a survey for the graduate students in any program ,specifically in the college of hospitality management. It is an important document that compiles data and profiles of the graduate , which enable each college to identify their program strength and weakness thus increase the success of the program or courses to increase their graduates prospects for employment .It also

identified the work related values and skills that contribute in meeting the demands of the industry. This tracer study or graduate study serves as the basis of curriculum review of the institution of each department to determine what needs to improve in their programs or courses.

The Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management is a program or courses offered by the university to mold and equip the students to work in the tourism and hospitality industry. The university is an incubation phase to prepare the students with the necessary skills, knowledge, attitudes and training they need to provide an excellent performance while working in the industry. In this program or course, the university offer subjects that the students need to know when they will manage or work in hospitality industry. The subjects provided or offered cover the different sector in the hospitality industry, such as, culinary and baking, front office, housekeeping, food and beverage, management and many more. The main objective of this program or course is to develop and mold the students who want to be a part of hospitality with the necessary knowledge and skills that they may use in achieving and reaching for their ambitions and dreams.

The researchers determine the success of both students and the program or course in terms of tracing the hospitality management graduates using a survey questionnaire, to know what factors needs to improve and what they really excel when offering this program.

The objective of the study is to determine the employability of the graduates of College of Hospitality Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus for the school year 2020-2023. Specifically, it seek to determine the job placement profile of the graduates and relevance of school related factors to job placement. It also identified the reason why graduates choose the hospitality Management course and the necessary skills that contribute in meeting the demands of the industry. Furthermore, this research proposes recommendations to improve employment rate for College of Hospitality Management program of the University.

Theoretical Background

The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on several key theories that provide insight into the employment status of Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM) graduates from the University of Cebu Main Campus. One of the foundational theories is Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964), which posits that investments in education and training enhance individuals' productivity and employability. In the context of BSHM graduates, their academic preparation, practical training, and industry-relevant skills are crucial determinants of their job opportunities and career progression. This theory underscores the importance of aligning the graduates' educational experiences with labor market demands to ensure their successful integration into the workforce.

Another relevant framework is Employability Theory (Hillage & Pollard, 1998), which defines employability as the ability of individuals to gain, maintain, and transition between jobs based on their skills, knowledge, and attitudes. This theory is essential in evaluating whether BSHM graduates possess the necessary competencies to meet the expectations of the hospitality industry. The tracer study will examine how effectively the academic program has equipped graduates with the skills needed for employment and whether there is a gap between their training and industry requirements.

Furthermore, Career Development Theory (Super, 1957; Holland, 1997) provides valuable insights into the career trajectories of BSHM graduates. Super's theory highlights that career choices evolve based on life experiences and personal development, while Holland's theory suggests that individuals select careers that align with their personality types. This perspective allows the study to assess whether graduates' current employment aligns with their academic training and personal career aspirations, shedding light on the factors influencing their job placement and professional growth.

The study is also grounded in School-to-Work Transition Theory (Raffe, 2003), which explains how students move from academic institutions to the workforce. This transition is influenced by factors such as curriculum design, internships, career services, and industry linkages. By applying this theory, the tracer study can evaluate the extent to which the University of Cebu's BSHM program prepares its graduates for employment, identifying areas of strength and potential gaps that need to be addressed for better industry alignment.

Lastly, Structural Functionalism (Parsons, 1951) provides a macro-level perspective on the role of education in workforce development. This theory views education as a system designed to prepare individuals for their roles in society, ensuring that graduates acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to meet industry demands. In this study, Structural Functionalism supports the analysis of whether the BSHM program effectively supplies the hospitality industry with qualified professionals and how well graduates integrate into the labor market.

These theoretical foundations collectively provide a strong analytical lens for understanding the employability, career trajectories, and workforce integration of BSHM graduates. By examining their employment status through these

frameworks, the study aims to generate insights that can inform curriculum improvements, strengthen industry linkages, and enhance graduate employability in the hospitality sector.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to assess the employability of graduates from the College of Hospitality Management at the University of Cebu-Main Campus for the academic years 2020–2023. Specifically, it seeks to analyze the graduates' job placement profiles and evaluate the relevance of school-related factors in their employment outcomes. Additionally, the study explores the reasons graduates chose the Hospitality Management program and identifies the key skills that contribute to meeting industry demands. Based on the findings, this research will propose recommendations to enhance the employment rate of Hospitality Management graduates.

Specifically, the study is guided by the following objectives:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Gender
 - Civil Status
 - Region of Origin
 - Current Address
2. To examine the educational background of the respondents, including:
 - Highest Educational Attainment
 - Postgraduate Studies
 - Postgraduate Training (TESDA NC II certifications)
 - Reasons for pursuing further education or training
3. To analyze the employment status of the respondents, focusing on:
 - Employment Status (Employed or Unemployed)
 - Reasons for Unemployment (if applicable)
 - Type of Employment (Regular, Contractual, Self-Employed, etc.)
 - Skills acquired in college that were applied in self-employment (if applicable)
 - Current employment in major hotel departments
 - Place of Work (Local or Overseas)
 - Whether the current job is their first employment after graduation
 - Reasons for job transitions or career shifts
 - Factors influencing job retention
 - Relevance of the first job to their college degree
 - Reasons for accepting their first job
 - Methods used to secure their first job (e.g., referrals, job fairs, online applications)
 - Current Job Position
 - Initial Gross Monthly Earnings
 - Relevance of the college curriculum to their first job
 - Competencies learned in college that were most useful in their first job

This research will provide insights into the alignment between the College of Hospitality Management's curriculum and the evolving demands of the hospitality industry. The findings will serve as a basis for refining academic programs, strengthening career support services, and enhancing industry linkages to improve graduates' employability.

Methodology

The research methodology presents the research design, phases of the study, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment used to interpret the collected data. The purpose of this study is to determine the employability of the graduates of College of Hospitality Management, University of Cebu-Main Campus for the school year 2020-2022. This study focuses on the graduates who completed Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management program. The graduates were invited to participate in the online tracer study, through their email addresses, using the Google Survey Form. The tracer study questionnaire has three parts namely: Part 1. Is the respondents' profile, 2. Is the Educational Background of the Graduates and 3. Is The employment data and status of the graduates and relevance of university related factors to the job placement of the respondents and skills developed by college of hospitality management University of Cebu Main campus and work – related values. A total of 81 graduates responded to the tracer online survey, with a response rate of 67.5%. These graduates have already graduated from their their course one to two years prior to the commencement of the tracer survey conducted from 2020 to 2022.

The data collected were tabulated and coded for analysis. The following statistical tools were employed in interpreting the data obtained from the survey: percentage was used to analyze the profile of the respondents with respect to

the selected variables; weighted mean was used to determine the degree of perception of the graduate respondents in the school factors related to their job placement; and Rank was utilized to will show the position of importance of the items used. It is important to mention, that the tables and graphs contained in this report only reflect the responses of the graduates from 2020 to 2022. participate in the Tracer Study. Moreover, the difficulty to locate and follow-up the graduates during the data collection, has caused a major constraint in targeting a high response rate.

Results and Discussion

2.1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

This section of the paper presents the results of the data gathered from the graduate students of University of Cebu – Main Campus who have taken the course of Hospitality Management from the school year 2020-2022.

2.1.1. Gender, Civil Status, Region of Origin , and Location of Residence.

The figure shows the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, civil status, region, province, and residence. It shows that there were 30 or 66.70% female respondents while 13 or 33.30% male respondents for its Gender.

Figure1 -Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

As for the Civil Status, all of the respondents are single 43 or 100% .

Table 1-Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

As for the Region of Origin, maturity of the graduates are from Region VII or Central Visayas Region , 2 or 4.8% from Region 8 and 10, while 1 or 2.4% of the graduates are from Region VI and IX.

Figure 2 -Profile of the Respondents in terms of Region of Origin

As for Location of Residence, 6 or 14% respondents are mostly located on the City while 37 or 86 % respondents are from the different Municipalities

Figure 3- 5-Profile of the Respondents in terms of Location of Residence

As for the respondents educational attainment, majority of the respondents 39 or 90% are BSHM graduates, while 1 or 6% are college level and both 1 or 2% pursue Master Degree and 1 or 6% pursue Doctoral Degree Course.

Table 2- Respondents Educational Background

The demographic profiles of the respondents implied that most of the respondents are a degree holder on Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management because of its assurance for their work applications while some of the graduates pursue graduate studies for them increase their educational qualification for future promotions in their respective companies and enhance more knowledge in the fast changing hospitality and tourism industry.

2.2. Educational Background

This part shows the data collated pertaining to the respondents educational background of the respondents in terms of: Educational Attainment; Post Graduate Studies, Post Graduate Training (TESDA NC II 's);Post Graduate Studies? And their reasons in pursuing those degrees?

Table 3 shows the respondents reasons of taking the course or pursue the Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management degree on . The main deciding factor why they choose the course is the opportunity for them to work abroad with a score of 59 or 75.6 % followed by the strong passion for the profession at 39 or 50%,Prospect for immediate employment at 31 or 39.70%, Influence of parents or relatives 20 or 25.60%

Status or prestige of the profession 12 or 15.40% 5Peer Influence 12 or 15.40% availability or course offering in chosen institution 11 or 14. %,Inspired by a role model 10or 2.80% ,affordable for the family 8 or 10.30%, Good grades in high school 4 or 5.10%,and at 1 or 1.30% is the reasons with no particular choice or no better idea.The results from table 2 implies that majority the graduates reasons of pursuing the course to go abroad after graduation and also they have a very strong passion in working in the hospitality industry.

Table 3- Reason(s) for taking the BSHRM/HM course(s) or pursuing degree(s)

Table 4 shows that respondents are very open in advancing themselves professionally by taking the national competency from TESDA and to increase their educational qualification through national certification from the said agency, most our graduates passed the following national competency; namely Bread and Pastry NC II 12or 32.40%,Food and Beverage Service NC II 9 or 24.30%, Cookery NC II 9 or 24.30%,Bar-tending Services NC II 3 or 8.10%, Front Office Services NC II 3 or 8.10%, Barista NC II 2 or 5.40%,Tour Guiding NC II 1 or 2.70%, Events Management NC II 1 or 2.70% and Food Processing and Preservation NC II 1 or 2.70%.

Table 4-Training/ TESDA National Certifications garnered and Advance Studies Attended .

The figure revealed that shows that 42 or 51.2% of the respondents are currently employed and used their degree to find a suitable job. While 38 or 47.5% are currently not employed for some reasons that the graduates are still looking for job or opted for self-employment. The table also implies that majority of the graduates find themselves employed but there is a substantial number of graduates who are not currently employed at this moment.

Figure 4-Employment Data

The table shows the reason why the respondents are unemployed. The following reasons are as follows; they pursue advance or further study 4 or 11.40%, Did not look for a job 13 or 37.10%, Family concern and decided not to find a job 3 or 8.60%, Health-related reason(s) 0 or 0%, Lack of work experience 6 or 17.10%, No job opportunity 9 or 25.70% and Other reason(s), at 4 or 11.40%.

Table 5-Please state reason(s) why you are not yet employed

The figure implied that, the respondents present employment status or tenure, the results are the following; Regular or Permanent 23 or 47.90%, Temporary 8 or 16.70%, Casual 9 or 18.80%, Self-employed 6 or 12.50%, Probationary 1 or 2.10%, and Other reasons at 1 or 2.10%. The result shows that majority of the respondent's employment status are at regular standing.

Figure 5-Present Employment Status

The table shows the respondents skills acquired in college were you able to apply in your in work, the following results are; bar tending 6 or 23.10%, waitering or F and B service 15 or 57.70%, Cooking 6 or 23.10%, Barista 4 or 15.40%, Baking 5 or 19.20%, Events and Catering 3 or 11.50%, Web Designing/Content Creator 3 11.50%, Media Influence r 0 or 0%, Housekeeping related business 6 or 23.10%, Front office related business 4 or 15.40%, Souvenir shops 0 or 0%, Airline Industry Management 2 or 7.70%, Tourism related business 5 or 19.20% and Academe/ Teaching Profession at 1 or 3.80%. The results shows that majority of the respondents acquired skills from college and it helps them during actual work in area of food and beverage.

Table 6-If self-employed, what skills acquired in college were you able to apply in your work?

The figure shows what hotel departments the respondents are currently working in the hotel or resorts, the results are the following; Food and Beverage (Waitring) 9 or 22.50%, Culinary 4 or 10%, Other or 10%, Housekeeping 3 or 11.10%, Food and Beverage (Barista) 3 or 7.50%, Sales and Marketing 3 or 7.50%, Housekeeping (Flowers/Landscaping) 3 or 7.50%, Business Center 3 or 7.50%, Front Office 1 or 3.70%, Food and Beverage (Bartending) 1 or 3.70%, Events/Catering 1 or 2.50%, Engineering and Maintenance 1 or 3.70%, and Finance and Accounting at 1 or 2.50%. The data shows that majority of respondents are assigned or currently working in the Food and Beverage Department.

Figure 7-Major hotel departments you are presently employed

The figure shows the geographical distribution of the respondent's place of work, The results shows that majority of the respondents at 42 or 91.30 % are working within the country and 4 or 8.79 % are working abroad.

Figure 8-Respondents Place of Work

The figure shows that majority at 24 or 52.20 % of the respondents first time working in the industry after college, and 22 or 47.80% states that it is not their first time working in the industry after they graduate from college.

Figure 9-Is this your first job after college?

The table shows that the main reasons why the reasons change their jobs are the following:Salaries & benefits 26 or 76.50%,Career challenge 19 or 55.90%, Related to special skills 14 or 41.20%, Proximity to residence 4 or 11.80%,Continue Studying 1 or 2.90%, and through Direct Hiring at 1or 2.90%.The main reason why the respondents change jobs is because of higher salaries offered by the property.

Table 7-What were your reason(s) for changing job?

The table shows the primary reasons, why the respondents opted to stay on their first job in the industry after they graduate from college, the following results are as follows;Salaries and benefits 32 or 72.70%,Career challenge 26 or 59.10%,Related to special skill 18 or .90%,Related to course or program of study 14 or 31.80%,Proximity to residence 5 or 11.40%, Peer influence 5 or 11.40%, Family influence 4 or 9.10% and Others reason at 1 or 2.30%.

The data shows that respondents main reason why they stay in their first job is that they happy with their salaries and wages provided by their respective companies.

Table 8-Respondents reason(s) for staying on the job?

The figure revealed that majority of the respondents current jobs are related to the course that they took in college which is the Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management at 30 or 69.8 % said yes and 13 or 30.20% said no respectively. The result also manifest that the present course program of the college is still relevant to the needs of the industry.

Figure 10-Is your first job related to the course you took up in college?

The table shows Respondents reasons for accepting their first job after graduation. The results are as follows: Salaries & benefits 34 or 79.10%, Career challenge 28 or 65.10%, Related to special skills 25 or 58.10%, Proximity to residence 6 or 14% ,For experience 1 or 2.30% and for Passion at 1 or 2.30%. The table reveals that the respondents main reason for accepting their first job is because the reasonable salaries and wages of the company followed by career challenge the respondents anticipated on their future job.

Table 9-What were your reasons for accepting the job?

The table shows the respondents on how they find their first job after graduation, the following results are as follows; As walk-in applicant 15 or 35.70%, Recommended by someone 15 or 35.70%, information from friends 12 or 28.60%, Response to an advertisement 10 or 20.4%, Family business 5 or 10.2%, Job Fair or Public Employment Service 1 or 2.40%, Absorbed from OJT 1 or 2.40% and arranged by school's job placement officer 0 or 0%. The shows that most respondents find their first job as walk-in applicants followed by recommendation from someone or word of mouth.

Table 10-How did you find your first job?

The figure shows the respondents answer to the question, how long did it take you to land your first job after graduation? The results are the following; Less than a month 12 or 27.30%, 1 to 6 months 12 or 27.30%, 7 to 11 months 6 or 13.60%, 1 year to less than 2 years 4 or 9.10%, 2 years to less than 3 years 1 or 2.30%, 3 years to less than 4 years 3 or 6.80% and others at 1 or 2.30%. It shows that it takes less than a month for the respondents to look for a job after graduation due to their absorption after internship training.

Figure 10-How long did it take you to land your first job after graduation?

The figure, shows the job level positions of the respondents in their respective properties, the results are as follows; Staff/rank level 31 or 70.50%, Managerial/Executive 4 or 9.10%, Supervisory 3 or 6.80%, Self-employed/Owner 3 or 6.80%, and other position at 1 or 2.30%. The table indicates that majority of the respondents occupies a staff or rank level positions in the hotel or restaurant.

Figure 11-Respondents Job Level Position?

The figure shows that the initial gross income of the respondents while working in the hotel and restaurant are as follows; P10,000.00 to less than P15,000.00 12 or 26.10%, P15,000.00 to less than P20,000.00 12 or 26.10%, P5,000.00 to less than P10,000.00 11 or 23.90%, Below P5,000.00 4 or 8.70%, P 20,000.00 to less than P25,000.00 , P 25,000.00 and above 3 or 6.50%, and others at 1 or 2.20%.

Figure 12-What is your initial gross monthly earning in your first job after college?

The figure revealed that the respondents response on the question. Was the curriculum you had in college relevant to your first job? The following results are as follows; Yes for the relevance of the curriculum at 41 or 89.10%, and the curriculum is not relevant at 5 or 10.90%. The results manifest that the college curriculum is still relevant to the needs of the industry as perceived by our respondents.

Figure 12- Was the curriculum you had in college relevant to your first job?

The Table shows the respondents perception on what competencies did they learned in college that they find very useful in their first job, The results are as follows; Communication skills 38 or 90.5, Human Relations skills 30 or 71.4, Critical Thinking skills 26 or 61.9, Problem-solving skills 25 or 59.5, Information Technology skills 15 or 35.7, Entrepreneurial skills 13 or 31 And other competencies at 1 or 2.4. The results manifest that communication skills followed by human relation skills are very important soft skills in the tourism and hospitality industry.

Table 11- what competencies learned in college did you find very useful in your first job?

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is then therefore concluded that majority of the respondents are female and single, most of them are residing in the province of Cebu and are graduates of the four-year program in Hospitality Management but some also pursue graduate school studies. Most of the graduates' reasons for choosing the program is to work abroad, and at present most of them are working in the industry on regular status and are rank staff status, and majority of them are presently working inside the country. There were also unemployed graduates and the main reasons for this is that they opted to go home to their home province and also lack of job opportunity in the city. One noticeable about our graduates is that they are open to further studies or undergo national certificates specifically in the food and beverage, read and Pastry and Housekeeping services.

The graduates also stated the relevance of their present curriculum to the needs of the industry and identified skills they acquired from school that helps them employable: e.g. food and beverage, bar tending and housekeeping services. It is also important to note that majority of our graduates are working in their field of study which is hospitality management, and are presently working in the Food and Beverage department of the hotel or resorts. On the questions of job motivation, most of them are positive on their salaries and wages and also the career challenges in the industry. The study also reveals that most of the graduates find their job less than one year after graduation due to strong linkage between the school and the properties and the graduates' most important soft skills that they feel important in the industry is communications skills followed by human relation skills which researcher also believed very important to the tourism and hospitality as a service-oriented industry. Findings of the study, it is therefore concluded that majority of the subjects is within the age bracket 17-18 years old; majority were female; majority of the subject got a grade of 2.0 to 2.6 as described as good and most of them belong to the Housekeeping Service NC II.

Recommendations

1. On the graduates' eagerness to work abroad after graduation, the college of Hospitality Management must strengthen their linkage between the existing and future job placement agencies and job placement programs of the student affairs office on catering students to work within the country or abroad as to maximize and facilitate graduates' employment.
2. Though majority of the graduates find job for less than a year after graduation, the college may also coordinate more on their hotel partners as to their latest or updates in relation to employment, at the same time the university must intensify their drive and service through their placement employment services.
3. The college also must closely coordinate with their graduate's status as through constant monitoring or tracing to help them with their employment plans and also give advice for those students who opted to study further instead of going directly for employment.
4. The college also update regularly the status of their graduates and ask for possible curriculum enhancement programs they could offer at the College. And also encourage the graduates to be more motivated to work hard and persevere in whatever task and project assigned to them to develop their sense of responsibility and leadership.

Their competencies may be further strengthened through exposure to various competitions and other related training and seminars and TESDA National Certifications. Further students to participate in the English Proficiency Programs to further enhance their communication and human relation skills. Workplace attitude, knowledge and skills of the hospitality management students must be given importance in the application of the outcomes-based curriculum.

Teachers handling general education and professional hospitality core courses must be encouraged to continue to update and enhance teaching skills through immersion programs hospitality and tourism related training and workshop seminars facilitated by the university. The college must continue to create linkages to major hotel and resort properties within the country and abroad that will increase employment rate of the graduates .

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